

ISic3015

I.Sicily inscription 3015

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

unknown

Material

Limestone

Object

fragment

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

2018.07.17 Prag

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Agrigentum

Place of origin (modern)

Agrigento

Provenance

unknown, previously in the collection of the Comune di Agrigento

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Agrigento, Museo Regionale Archeologico Pietro Griffo, inventory C1868

Physical Description

A fragment of a porous yellow stone rich in shell fragments, damaged on all sides, and now mounted in a plaster block (dimensions measured on the visible remains, not of the entire plaster block).

Dimensions

Height 22.5 cm

Width 41.5 cm

Depth 11.5 cm

Layout

Remains of two lines of greek letters, deeply incised

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: 65-85 mm

Line 2: 60+ (incomplete) mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: 5 mm

Text

1. [---]σλας · Δ[---]

2. [---]ναλο[---]

Apparatus

Text after autopsy

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645363
EDR 136012
PHI 336046

Bibliography

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Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-18): ISic3015. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4357082>

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